

INSTALLATION OF AUTO CAD SOFTWARE AND STUDY OF PANELS IN THE FIELD OF COMPUTER GRAPHICS

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Annotation: The article discusses how to increase the effectiveness of students' reading using modern technologies in teaching computer graphics. Students will learn about the three-dimensional design capabilities of AutoCAD and how to create a three-dimensional environment in the user interface.

Keywords: AutoCAD, drawing, sketch, drawing, projection design, detail.

INTRODUCTION

In modern education, the role of human activity in the creation and introduction of new technologies in all sectors of our developing independent state is determined. Young educators are required to have in-depth knowledge not only in their field, but also in modern information technology and to teach it to young people, especially students. Informatics and information technologies are rapidly developing and improving in the world. The latest technologies are being introduced in Uzbekistan. It is no coincidence that the 21st century is the age of computer technology. Nowadays, with the development of modern techniques, all schools use modern information technology. According to today's requirements, teachers of engineering graphics should have a basic knowledge of at least five modern graphics programs and they should be able to use them to design promotional elements of drawing on a computer, such as Photo Shop, Corel Draw, 3D MAX, AutoCAD and Flash. Because it is impossible to imagine the development of any modern e-learning materials without these programs.

AutoCAD was the first to solve the problem we faced, and although it is now almost 30 years since the creation of the program, which is now an international

standard for automated design, it still remains popular among graphics programs. AutoCAD is a perfect and popular program, as well as an automated design program that performs all types of schemes and drawings with high accuracy and quality. It also guarantees that the program will fully realize the creative potential of its users. Therefore, it has become common for millions of designers, scientists, engineers and students from more than 80 countries to use AutoCAD to design in 18 languages.

Educators have a task to bring up the younger generation in accordance with modern requirements. We need to inculcate in the minds of our young people the concepts of Independent Uzbekistan, Homeland and breathe with the world. teaching the procedure and rules of computer-aided imaging. The main task of the subject "Computer Graphics" is to ensure that the teacher has the knowledge and skills necessary for students to freely perform design and creation of models of technological processes on a computer using modern lectures and practical and operational programs and ready-made packages. Students should be able to read the drawings, perform them, collect graphic information, draw diagrams.

It is known that before coming to the university, if students have the necessary basic knowledge and skills in the field of "Computer Graphics", they will develop the spatial imagination, the ability to read drawing, which is necessary in the science of graphics. This suggests that it is advisable to start this course with a secondary special, vocational education system. Thanks to the scientific research of a number of researchers in this area, practical results are being achieved that can have a great impact on the educational process.

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Figure 1. Start AutoCAD

AutoCAD system tab.

You can also start AutoCAD using a shortcut. To do this, double-click on the AutoCAD system tab in the desktop menu with the left mouse button. The result is the graphical interface of AutoCAD.

Enter information using the keyboard and press Enter. When prompted to enter one or more commands on the command line, type the initials of the command and press Enter. For example, switching to zoom mode is done by pressing the "R" and "Enter" keys instead of the "Reference" command. Everyone needs to be able to use

computers effectively in their work. In short, the user must first learn computer graphics, then computer science, then drawing and drawing geometry.

CONCLUSION

In short, it is impossible to master computer graphics without knowing a set of simple operations on a computer. This means that in the education system, computer science must first be mastered by students. Since AutoCAD graphics software is related to drawing creation, it also requires knowledge of specific sciences such as drawing, geometry, and drawing geometry, which is the theory of the science of drawing. Independent learning and control in the education system is one of the main factors of independent learning. In order to acquire independent knowledge, first of all, it is necessary to form in students the need for independent work, free, creative activity.

According to the research of psychologist A. Maslow, the pyramid of human needs can be seen as a creative approach to this issue. From the pyramid, we can see that as human needs increase, so does the pursuit of perfection. In order to reach maturity, students need to develop the qualities of activity, independence, curiosity. In addition, future professionals face in their practice such processes as reduced ability to work, fatigue, exhaustion, work, rest.

This means that the judicious use of AutoCAD software is a topical issue that requires independent reading and drawing.

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